

local check Ambemohor (see table). In minikit trials conducted in farmer fields

in 1981 (28 trials in 3 districts) and 1982 (76 trials in 6 districts), PBN1 yielded 2.5

t/ha in 1981 and 4.1 t/ha in 1982. Ambe-mohor yielded 2.3 and 3.4 t/ha. □

Screening rice varieties for salt tolerance in Bangladesh

G. J. U. Ahmed and K. U. Ahmed, *BRR1 Regional Station, Sonagazi, Noakhali, Bangladesh*

Salinity limits rice cultivation on about 1 million ha of land in southern Bangladesh.

We developed a simple, low-cost screening method to identify rice varieties with salt tolerance. Nearly neutral dried

Table 1. Salt-tolerant varieties or lines isolated in Bangladesh.

Variety, line	Score ^a
<i>Aus</i>	
BR1	3
BR203-26-2	3
BR201-193-1	4
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)	3
Pajam (susceptible check)	9
<i>Aman</i>	
BR4	4
BR10	4
Rajasail	3
Kajalsail	3
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)	3
Pajam (susceptible check)	9

^aVisual scoring 1-9: 1-4 = almost healthy plant, 7-9 = almost dead plant.

soil was placed in a petri dish and an NaCl solution was added to the soil to adjust the electrical conductivity to 10 dS/m and salinity level was monitored throughout the experiment. Twenty seeds of each variety or line were sown in the petri dish. IR9884-54-3 was used as resistant check and Pajam, the susceptible check. Germinated seeds were grown in the petri dish 21 d. Salt injury was scored by the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

In the 1982 screening of 50 varieties or lines, 3 aus season varieties (BR1, BR203-26-2, and BR201-193-1) and 4

aman varieties (BR4, BR10, Rajasail, and Kajalsail) were salt tolerant (Table 1).

Those varieties and lines were tested in a saline field in replicated yield trials. In 1983 aus, BR201-193-1 and BR203-26-2 were tested with local check variety Chicknal. They were direct seeded by dibbling at 20- × 15-cm spacing and fertilizer 60 kg N and 40 kg P/ha were applied. They yielded more than twice the local check variety (Table 2).

In 1983 BR4 and BR10 were tested in t. aman under uniform conditions. The local variety Kajalsail was used as check. BR4 and BR10 yielded best (Table 2). □

Table 2. Yield and related characters of salt-tolerant rice.

Variety, line	Flowering date	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Aus</i> ^a					
BR201-193-1	7 Jun 83	112	121.0	425	3.96
BR203-26-2	17 Jun 83	127	104.0	457	6.65
Chicknal (check)	15 May 83	90	97.0	247	1.50
<i>Aman</i> ^b					
BR4	26 Oct 82	138	102.0	344	3.60
BR10	22 Oct 82	137	98.0	378	4.0
Kajalsail (check)	5 Nov 82	154	140.0	210	1.6

^aSeeded 9 Mar 83. ^bSeeded 30 Jun 82.

Salinity-mediated enhancement of harvest index of rice — selection criterion for salt tolerance

T. N. Singh, *Crop Physiology Department, N. C. University of Agriculture and Technology, Faizabad, U. P., India*

Soil salinity inhibits rice production in almost every country. It is important to develop salt-tolerant rice varieties to increase rice production in areas with saline soil.

We studied the effects of saline soils on harvest index (HI) (grain:straw) of rice at the Salinity Institute, Karnal. Four rice varieties were planted at 5 salinity levels (ECe 1.2, 5.6, 8.7, 13.0 and 16.0 dS/m) in 18-kg porcelain pots. NaCl:CaCl₂ at 4:1 was mixed in sandy loam soil. The soil was saturated and 35-day-old seed-

1. Yield reductions of rice varieties by salinity.

2. Trend of change in harvest index of rice varieties by salinity.

lings were planted at 3 seedlings/hill, 4 hills/pot. Treatments were replicated four times, Before transplanting, 15 g ammonium sulfate, 8 g superphosphate, and 3 g muriate of potash were added to each pot. An additional 7 g of ammonium sulfate was topdressed at maximum tillering and at heading. Standing water level was kept at 4 cm by adding tubewell water.

Salinity as high as ECe 5.6 dS/m did

not adversely affect grain yield (Fig. 1), but increasing salinity abruptly reduced yield of Jaya, RP107-11, and IET1991 (Sona). Pusa 2-21 yield did not decline sharply with increased salinity. At the highest salinity level Pusa 2-21 showed the least yield reduction and yielded highest.

In addition to affecting plant growth and yield, salinity altered the grain-straw

ratio. HI increased from 1.3 to 1.6 in Pusa 2-21 with salinity to ECe 5.6 dS/m and remained at similar or slightly higher values up to ECe 8.7 dS/m (Fig. 2).

HI decreased steadily for Jaya as salinity increased. RF107-11 HI did not change up to ECe 8.7 dS/m, but later declined sharply. IET1991 had lowest HI under saline conditions. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Breeding varieties for rainfed upland situations

U. Prasado Rao, AN India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Hyderabad 30, India

About a decade ago rice breeding programs in India began to emphasize development of drought-tolerant early-maturing varieties for drought-prone uplands. In 1975 AICRIP began breeding

for such lines to produce reasonably good yields.

In 1975, 35 crosses of high yielding varieties Rasi, RP79-5, Cauvery, Akashi, and OR34-16 were made with the following drought-tolerant parents: 63-83, TOS4020, TOS4617, Rikuto Norin 21, Kinandang Puti, IRAT8, Merikrak, Mettasanna, Tellavadlu, N22, Fine gora, Black gora, Sarya, Kalamsu, RPA5824, CR143-2-10, IET5850, and JBS446.

F₁ and F₂ populations (more than

5,000 plants/cross) were transplanted and selected for early vigor, tillering precocity, synchronous flowering, and early maturity. Beginning with F₃, selections were alternately direct-seeded and transplanted. Reaction to blast (B1) and rice tungro virus (RTV) was studied at F₄-F₆, and drought tolerance was evaluated at every stage. Homogeneous selections were bulked and yield tested in F₅.

Nine cultures from six crosses had consistently better performance than

Table 1. Promising short-duration upland cultures developed at AICRIP. ^a

IET no.	Designation and cross	Direct seeding		Transplanting		Grain type ^b	Drought sustenance	Seed dormancy (days)	Reaction ^c to	
		Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)				Blast	RTV
7564	RP1667-301-6-1196-1562 (IRAT 8 / N22)	90	4.5	95	5.4	LS	23	6	R	MR
7566	RP1670-1418-2205-1585 (M63-83 / Cauvery)	95	4.4	99	5.4	LB	22	6	R	S
7613	RP1670-1418-2205-1582 (M63-83 / Cauvery)	90	3.5	95	4.5	LB	23	6	R	S
7617	RP1888-4259-1529-126 (RP79-5 / Tellavadlu)	90	4.0	98	5.2	LB	25	5	R	S
7633	RP1451-1196-1562-4218 (Rasi / Fine gora)	90	3.8	98	4.6	LS	21	6	R	MR
7265	RP1899-1481-78-1 (IET5850 / OR34-16)	95	3.5	100	4.6	LB	25	5	R	S
7614	RP1451-1712-4319 (Rasi / Fine gora)	90	3.5	100	4.4	LS	24	5	R	S
7635	RP1667-4218-1 (IRAT8 / N22)	89	3.3	100	4.4	LS	23	7	R	MR
7261	RP1897-3790-30-1 (Rasi / Mettasanna)	100	4.1	105	4.5	LS	22	—	R	MR
	Akashi	100	3.0	105	4.0	SB	15	10	R	S
	N22	100	2.6	105	2.8	SB	16	15	—	S
	ADT31	120	2.1	125	3.4	LB	10	—	—	S
	IET7281 (IR50)	110	2.4	115	4.1	LS	10	—	—	—
	Tellahamsa	110	2.0	115	3.0	LS	11	—	—	S
	Sattari	90	1.9	90	2.8	SB	12	—	—	S
	Cauvery	108	3.1	110	4.1	LB	10	—	MR	S
	Rasi	110	3.2	115	4.2	MS	15	5	R	S
	CD (0.05%)		1.25		2.24					

^a Rainfall during the season was 469.5 mm. ^b LB = long bold, LS = long slender. SB = short bold. ^c R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.